

Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing Library Services to Students in Universities in Taraba State

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Abstract:- Library organizations are well known as centers for information generation and retrieval systems. The achievement of this core objective is determined solely on how such a library stick to a working collection development policy. This research work has taken to investigate the value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in universities in Taraba State. The study sets three objectives and three research questions to investigate the value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in universities in Taraba State. This research study adopted a descriptive survey research design for data collection. A total population for the research investigation was 11,258 registered students' library users from the three universities under investigations. A sample size of 563 was used for the study. The research study used a modified structured questionnaire as the instrument for data collection which titled: 'Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing Library Services to Students in Universities (VCDPELSS)'. The researcher adopted a descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation for data analysis. The study revealed the findings that collection development policy has significant mean value in enhancing all library services and activities in University Libraries in Taraba State. The study therefore, presented the following recommendations; that the university libraries management in Taraba State should corroborate with the state government and other philanthropies and organizations to ensure that enough funds are provide for the general operations of university libraries activities and services. The management of the university libraries should employ well trained and skilful collection developers who can build up the library collections covering all disciplines in their universities. Training and retraining of libraries staff should be encouraged among all the libraries staff. Adequate security measures should be taken to control library crime so that

information resources acquired will be adequately used. When all these are put in to cognizance the university Libraries in Taraba State could compete globally with other university libraries in the world.

I. INTRODUCTION

The creditability of library resources and services in supporting the academic needs of every university through learning, teaching and research is determined by a working collection development policy. Collection development policy is a road map that directs professional librarians on how best library services and activities can be adequately articulated in enhancing the academic activities of its parents' organization. It's therefore, means that any university library that neglect to adopt a written collection development policy will not only be declined but could as well shrine hence library organizations are regards as living organism. Their survival is depending on how well they are properly stocked.

Library organizations serve as the centers for information organization and retrieval systems. The effectiveness and efficiency of every library organization depend on how well the library builds its collections. Collection development policy is a systematic guideline or principles that help collection developers in building valuable and standard library collections.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

Collection development policy guides the collection developers in building the library's collections. It is an essential tool used by the library professionals for developing library collections; the core objectives of the library organizations are determined by a well functional and

application of collection development policy to be achieved. It builds the library collections which aimed at supporting the high population of teaching, learning, research and other academic activities of its parent's establishment to a high extent. University libraries are highly expected to ensure effectiveness and efficiency of its services in order to achieve the objectives, goals and mission of its parent's establishment. Professional librarians might likely acquire excess library resources in some disciplines at the expense of other disciplines if collection development policies are not strictly followed in the process.

The resultant effect is that such libraries might have high volume of library resources but might not be able to meet up with the information needs of its user's community. It is an established fact that universities could hardly progress without adequate supply of information resources to its user's community for teaching, learning and research activities. Libraries are living organism they can grow or shrive and this assertion can only be fulfilled where libraries adhered to collection development policy. This can therefore, be deduced that no library can adequately satisfy the information needs of its user's community without a functional collection development policy rather such libraries can only succeed to operate at decline or shrive instead of growing. It is on the account of this background that this research seeks to assess the value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in universities in Taraba State.

➤ *Objectives*

The general objective of this research study is to assess the Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing Library Services to Students in Universities in Taraba State. Specifically, this research seeks to:

- Examine the value of collection development policy in enhancing selection of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State.
- Find the value of collection development policy in enhancing acquisition of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State.
- Establish the value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in university libraries in Taraba State.

➤ *Research Questions*

This research study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing selection of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State?
- What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing acquisition of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State?
- What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in university libraries in Taraba State?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Collection development is the assembling of library resources in both prints and non prints formats. It is described as an essential process in building library collections. Collection development is the most important process in ensuring the effective and efficient performances of every library organizations. The concept of collection development is a complex terms view differently by many researchers and scholars but the view which paves ways for many researchers is the model of Evans. Collection development according to Evans, (2019) is a dynamic, self-perpetuating cycle or process and consists of six definable stages namely, community analysis, selection, acquisition, weeding and evaluation. Evan views that collection development has different stages in other words fundamental elements with which a library collections can be properly built. Johnson, (2018) defined collection development as a process which include selecting materials, collection development policy, collection maintenance, budget, users' needs assessment, collection assessment, cooperation and resource sharing in the process of collection development. Collection development therefore, involves some stages in process which geared towards building standard library collections. According to Okogwu and Ekere (2018), collection development is the selection, acquisition, and processing of library materials in various formats while putting the current and future information needs of users in mind. They further opined that, it is the systematic building of a library collection that is based on meaningful data rather than subjective choice. It also includes researching new and popular books and authors, reading reviews, listening to the needs of library patrons, planning for new collections, replacing lost or damaged materials, weeding the collection, formulation of selection criteria, planning for resource sharing, as well as routine selection and de-selection decisions. For effective and efficient determination of a meaningful collection development process a statistical data has to be taken with regards to the needs. IFLA, (2022) considers collection development as the ongoing assessments of the

information needs of library clientele, using statistics, analysis, and demographic projections. The assessment of users needs guides the collection developers in selecting and acquiring the relevant resources that can be of value to the users' community. Khayal, (2013) defined collection development as the activities that involved in assessing the users' needs, evaluating the present collection, determining the selection policy, coordinating the selection of items, re-evaluating and storing parts of the collection and planning for resource sharing. Collection development builds library collections to support the academic needs where learning, teaching and research activities can adequately be displayed. Ashikuzzaman (2018) noted that collection development can be achieved through acquisition of materials by way of purchase, gifts/grants, donations, legal deposits, institutional membership or exchange.

Collection development is the blue prints for developing the library's collections while collection development policy is the systematic guidelines for maintenance and expansion of library services and activities. Collection development policy has become necessary in the library collections processes and activities as it serves as a standard tool for measuring the standard of library collections. Johnson (2018); Patel (2016) views collection development policy as the selection policy or acquisition policy as it encompasses both the selection and acquisition policies as well as policies regarding evaluation, weeding, and discarding of materials. The phrase has been considered differently by many information professionals and scholars. According to Johnson (2018), collection development policies are written documents or rules and regulations guiding the selection, acquisition, evaluation, weeding, and accepting or rejecting of gifts. Collection development policy creates different means by which library resources can be acquired in collection development process. Eze & Eze (2016) affirmed that collection development policy is a document that contains a list of guidelines as to what is suitable for requisition in a particular library. Frempong-kore (2021) observes that the existence of collection development policy in academic libraries is the anchor that guides and directs the collection development activities by helping in the selection and acquisition processes of resources into the library. It serves as a guide in the process of library collection building and also helps to strengthen the collection. Rutherford (2022) opted that collection development policy typically defines an organizational approach, provides a framework for the collection and maintenance of materials, and ensures a consistency and transparency of methods. The value of collection development policy in enhancing library activities in every library organizations cannot be downplayed

with as without it the library could not meet the objectives, mission and needs of its parent's institution of establishment.

Library services are general routines of activities carry out by the library staff towards satisfying the information needs of their clientele. According to Omekwu (2006), library services are meant to support organizations, institutions and research by facilitating access to a libraries extensive range of information resources and challenges. Library services are offers to library users through the provision of information needs based on their context. Information professionals in the position of rendering these services are highly expected to be at the forefront by providing the timely and accurate information needs to their clientele. Considering the high rate of information needs globally, librarians are expected to be at the forefront as the information custodians to render extensive library services to user's community at ease so as to meet their information needs. The duties of librarians are to provide fair, justice, equity and reliable services to the users as well as the society in general. This is supported by Jogan, (2015) who opined that the core values must be well articulated and knowledge supported with commitment that would help in upholding individual and collective responsibilities towards knowledge access and provision, doing right and upholding professionalism from the foundation of quality services delivery to the users' community.

III. METHODOLOGY

The method adopted for this study is descriptive survey research design for data collection and analysis. The targeted population for this study consists of 11,258 students registered university libraries users comprising of three universities under investigation in Taraba State. The sample size for this study was 563 students registered library users representing 5% of the total population of 11,258 students registered library users in the universities under investigation. A modified structured Questionnaire developed by the researcher for data collection. A four point rating scale of 4= Strongly Agreed, 3= Agreed, 2= Disagreed and 1= Strongly Disagreed were used in answering the research questions. Data gathered from the research study areas were analyzed using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions.

IV. ANALYSIS OF DATA

➤ Research Question 1.

What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing the selection of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the mean Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing the Selection of Library Resources for Students in University Libraries in Taraba State

S/N	Items	N	SA	A	D	SD	Sum	Mean	S/D	Remark
1	Cdp has great mean value to enhance selection of library resources	563	477	37	34	15	2102	3.7336	0.69060	Accepted
2.	A greater percentage of library grow in a systematic arrangement as a result of cdp	563	476	53	21	13	2118.	3.7620	0.62866	Accepted
3.	The current trend of library resources in the society today is based on the value of cdp	563	477	51	24	11	2120	3.7655	0.61859	Accepted
4.	A good cdp means a good selection of library resources	563	481	42	16	24	2106	3.7407	0.71104	Accepted
5.	A careful selection of library resources that aimed at meeting the targeted needs of the users justify the implementation of cdp	563	471	46	17	29	2085	3.7034	0.76100	Accepted

Strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly disagree d(SD), and Disagreed (D)

Source: Field Study, 2024

The results obtained from Table 1 showed that all the items have the means scored that is highly above the cut-off point benchmark of 2.50. Item 1 has the mean scored of 3.7336, item 2 has the mean scored of 3.7520, item 3 has the mean scored of 3.7665, item 4 has the mean scored of 3.7407 and item 5 has the mean scored of 3.7034. This shows that collection development policy has significant mean value in enhancing the selection of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State.

➤ Research Question 2.

What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing the acquisition of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the mean Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing the Acquisition of Library Resources for Students in University Libraries in Taraba State

S/N	Items	N	SA	A	D	SD	Sum	Mean	S/D	Remark
1	Cdp helps to promote the acquisition of textbooks for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact resources to acquire	563	455	43	35	30	2049	3.6394	0.82208	Accepted
2.	Cdp helps to promote the acquisition of journals for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact journals to acquire	563	446	56	37	24	2050	3.6412	0.78637	Accepted
3.	Cdp helps to promote the acquisition of reference books for student as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire	563	481	43	22	17	2114	3.7549	0.66720	Accepted
4.	Cdp helps to promote resource sharing for students in universities as it adds volume to the already existing collections	563	477	46	28	12	2114	3.7549	0.64274	Accepted

5	Cdp helps to promote the acquisition of newspapers for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire	563	502	41	18	2	2169	3.8526	0.45970	Accepted
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Strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly disagreed (SD), and Disagreed (D)

Source: Field Study, 2024

The results obtained in Table 2 showed that all the items in the table have the calculated mean value of above 2.50 set as the cut-off benchmark for scoring. This showed that collection development policy has significant mean value in enhancing the acquisition of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State.

➤ *Research Question 3.*

What is the mean value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in university libraries in Taraba State?

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the Mean Value of Collection Development Policy in Enhancing Library Services to Students in University Libraries in Taraba State.

S/N	Items	N	SA	A	D	SD	Sum	Mean	S/D	Remark
1.	Cdp has value to enhance CAS to students in universities	563	493	31	29	10	2133.	3.7886	0.61396	Accepted
2.	Cdp has value to enhance SDI Services to students in universities	563	488	32	26	17	2117	3.7602	0.67575	Accepted
3.	Cdp has value to enhance IS to students in universities	563	472	34	29	28	2076	3.6874	0.78575	Accepted
4.	Cdp has value to enhance ILLS to students in universities	563	512	30	18	6	2177	3.8668	0.46017	Accepted
5	Cdp has value to enhance RS to students in universities	563	483	40	25	5	2117	3.7602	0.65706	Accepted

Strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly disagreed (SD), and Disagreed (D)

Source: Field Study, 2024

The results obtained in Table 3 showed the calculated mean scores of items 1-5 are above 2.50 as the cut-off point set as the benchmark for scoring. The standard deviation scored from 0.54477 and above for all the 5 items which shows that collection development policy has significant value to enhance library services to students in university libraries in Taraba State.

V. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this research study has proven that collection development policy is a necessary instrument in all library services and activities as without it the library organization could not achieved the objectives, goals, mission and needs of its parents establishment.

The first objective of the study was to examine the value of collection development policy in enhancing selection of library resources for students in university libraries in Tararba State. The responses from the opinions of the respondents in Table 1 showed that, collection development policy has

significant mean value to enhance selection of library resources in all the five items in the table. Item 1 in Table 1 which stated that cdp has great mean value to enhance selection of library resources, out of the 563 respondents, 477 strongly agreed, 37 agreed, 34 disagreed while only 15 strongly disagreed with the view that collection development policy does not has significant mean value to enhance selection of library resources. This gave the mean value scored of 3.7336 and standard deviation of 0.69060. Item 2 Table 1 stated that a greater percentage of library grow in a systematic arrangement as a result of cdp, out of the total respondents of 563, 476 strongly agreed, 53 agreed, 21 disagreed while only 13 disagreed. This gave us the mean value scored of 3.7620 and standard deviations value scored of 0.62866. This indicated that a greater percentage of libraries grow in a systematic arrangement as a result of Cdp. Item 3 Table 1 stated that the current trend of library resources in the society today is based on the value of cdp, out of 563 respondents, 477 strongly agreed, 51 agreed, 24 disagreed while only 11 respondents disagreed, this gave the mean value scored of 3.7655 and standard deviation value scored of 0.61859. This

indicated that the current trend of library resources in the society today is based on the value of cdp. Item 4 in table 1 stated that a good cdp means a good selection of library resources, out of the 563 respondents on this item 481 strongly agreed, 42 agreed, 16 strongly disagreed while only 24 strongly disagreed; the mean value obtained on this item was 3.7407, standard deviation value scored of 0.71104. This indicated that a good cdp means a good selection of library resources. Item 5 Table 1 stated that a careful selection of library resources that aimed at meeting the targeted needs of the users justify the implementation of cdp, out of the 563 respondents, 471 strongly agreed, 46 agreed, 29 disagreed while 29 strongly disagreed, this item has the mean scored value of 3.7034 and standard deviation value scored. This showed that a careful selection of library resources that aimed at meeting the targeted needs of the users justify the implementation of collection development policy.

The second objective was to find the value of collection development policy in enhancing acquisition of library resources for students in university libraries in Taraba State. Table 2 which answered the research question related to this objective has 5 items in total. The responses from the view of the respondents are as follows: items 1 cdp helps to promote the acquisition of textbooks for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact resources to acquire, out of 563 respondents 455 strongly agreed, 43 agreed, 35 disagreed and 30 strongly disagreed, the mean value scored of 3.6394 and the standard deviation value scored of 0.82208 which indicated that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of textbooks for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact resources to acquire. Item 2 stated that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of journals for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact journals to acquire, out of the 563 respondents 446 strongly agreed, 56 agreed, 37 disagreed and 24 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value of 3.6412 scored and standard deviation value scored of 0.78637 which showed that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of journals for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on the exact journals to acquire. Item 3 stated that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of reference books for students as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire. Out the 563 respondents 481 strongly agreed, 43 agreed, 22 disagreed while 17 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.7549 and standard deviation scored value of 0.66720. This indicated that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of reference books for students as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire. Item 4 stated that cdp helps to promote resource sharing for students

in universities as it adds volume to the already existing collections, out of the 563 respondents 477 strongly agreed, 46 agreed, 28 disagreed while 12 respondents strongly disagreed. The item recorded the mean value of 3.7549 scored and standard deviation value scored of 0.64274 which showed that cdp helps to promote resource sharing for students in universities as it adds volume to the already existing collections. Item 5 stated that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of newspapers for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire. Out of the 563 respondents, 502 strongly agreed 41 agreed, 18 disagreed while 2 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.8526 and the standard deviation value scored of 0.45970 this showed that cdp helps to promote the acquisition of newspapers for students in universities as it guides the acquisition librarian on which resources to acquire.

The third objective for this research work was to establish the value of collection development policy in enhancing library services to students in university libraries in Taraba State. This objective answered research question 3 in Table 3 analysis as follow: Item 1 stated that cdp has value to enhance CAS to students in universities, out of the 563 respondents 493 strongly agreed, 31 agreed, 29 disagreed while 10 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.7886 and standard deviation value scored of 0.61396. This showed that cdp has value to enhance CAS to students in universities. Item 2 in table 3 stated that cdp has value to enhance SDI services to students in universities, out of the 563 respondents 488 strongly agreed, 32 agreed, 26 disagreed and 17 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value of 3.7602 and the standard deviation of 0.67575. This indicated that cdp has value to enhance SDI services to students in universities. Item 3 in Table 3 stated that cdp has value to enhance IS to students in universities, out of the 563 respondents that participated in answering the research question 472 strongly agreed, 34 agreed 29 disagreed and 28 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.6874 and the standard deviation value scored of 0.78575. This indicated that cdp has value to enhance IS to students in universities. Item 4 in Table 3 stated that cdp has value to enhance ILLS to students in universities, out of the 563 respondents that participated in answering the research questions 512 strongly agreed, 30 agreed 18 disagreed while 6 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.8668 and the standard deviation scored value of 0.46017. This showed that cdp has value to enhance ILLS to students in universities. Item 5 in Table 3 stated that cdp has value to enhance RS to students in universities, out of the 563 respondents that participated in answering the research

questions 483 strongly agreed, 40 agreed, 25 disagreed while 5 strongly disagreed, the item has the mean value scored of 3.7602 and standard deviation value scored of 0.65706. This indicated that cdp has value to enhance RS to students in universities.

VI. CONCLUSION

Information is paramount and has become an important commodity in the society today. Research has shown that an informed nation is a developed nation as well as an informed person is a developed person, this explained why some nations has greater advantage than others as well as some individuals has advantages than others as a result of their access to the sources and resources of information they were able to accessed. Libraries are refers as the sources of information generations, organizations, retrieval and disseminations systems. The attainment of this core objective of library organization is depending on where the library adopts a functional and working collection development policy where all the library services and activities could be adequately articulated towards meeting the information needs of the users. Collection development policy is described as an indispensable tool in the collection building of every university library as a result of the role it plays in resources building of every university library. University libraries in Taraba state dearly needs practicing collection development guided by a working policy for effective and efficient library services that could adequately satisfy the information needs of their parents' establishment.

RECOMMENDATION

With reference to this research findings, the researcher recommended that the management of the university libraries in Taraba State should lease with the government so that adequate fund will be provided for running the university libraries activities with the aimed of supporting the academic activities of their universities. The researcher also recommended that other organizations, well meaningful individuals and philanthropies should support the university libraries by donating some funds for the smooth operations of the university libraries in Taraba State.

For adequate execution and implementation of collection development policy that could enhance effective library services in university libraries in Taraba State, skillful and well trained library professionals should be employed in carrying out the library services and activities. This will go along way by ensuring that such professionals are skillful

enough to identifying relevant information resources that can cut across the whole disciplines in the universities without been bias or excesses before acquisition.

The university libraries should engage in collaborative collection development to ease their collection activities and add volume and relevant resources to their library organizations.

Lastly, adequate security measures should be taken to control library crime so that information resources acquired will be adequately used.

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